

ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD EFFECTS IN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This work is focused on the development of multi-physics models to study the effects of coupling of mechanical, electromagnetic, and associated thermal fields in electrified carbon fiber polymer matrix composites. The particular emphasis is placed on the electric-current carrying composites and their deformation.

Keywords: Carbon fiber polymer composites; Electric current; Electro-magneto-thermo-mechanical coupling

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials lend themselves naturally to the concept of multifunctionality – where a material or structure performs more than one function. These multiple functions are typically structural (i.e. load bearing) plus one or more of a variety of other functions such as energy storage, actuation, damage sensing, etc. Multifunctionality can be achieved through interaction of mechanical, electromagnetic, thermal, and other fields. Our interest in this area is investigation of electro-magneto-thermo-mechanical coupling in composites and this work is a continuation of an ongoing research effort [1-4] in this direction.

Our recent experimental studies [2-4] included a series of low velocity impact tests on electrified unidirectional and cross-ply carbon fiber polymer matrix composites. The tests had been carried out under 0A, 25A, and 50A DC electric current applied to the composites plates. The results of measurements showed considerable dependence of the impact-induced damage upon the intensity of the electric field applied to the composite. In particular, when an electric current of 25 A and 50 A was applied to a unidirectional carbon fiber polymer matrix composite plate, the maximum load sustained by the plate had increased up to 24.7% and 43.6%, respectively. The effect of an electric field on cross-ply composites is quite different: application of current to cross-ply composite plates reduces significantly the amount of the impact damage and increases the amount of the absorbed energy, but does not alter the maximum load sustained by the composite. For example, none of the tested cross-ply plates carrying 50 A DC electric current were perforated in the impact tests at V_{50} velocity determined in tests with no current applied to the plates. Moreover, a direct relation was noticed between the field applied to the composite and the propagation of the impact damage: the stronger was the applied field, the less damage was observed in the experiments. The aforementioned

results were valid for the case when an electric current is applied immediately before the impact. Remarkably, it has been determined that prolonged application of an electric current to the carbon fiber polymer matrix composites leads to a significant Joule heating that eliminates the positive effect of the short-term current application.

The present work is focused on the development of multi-physics models to study the effects of coupling of mechanical, electromagnetic, and associated thermal fields in electrified carbon fiber polymer matrix composites.

ELECTRO-MAGNETO-THERMO-MECHANICAL COUPLING IN COMPOSITES

The carbon fiber polymer matrix composites consist of the electrically conductive carbon fibers and dielectric polymer matrix, and are electrically conductive at the macroscale. Therefore, simultaneous application of mechanical and electromagnetic loads to such materials results in a complex interaction of mechanical, electromagnetic, and associated thermal fields. Mathematically speaking, the problem reduces to solving of equations of motion, Maxwell's electrodynamic equations, and heat transfer equations. Here we discuss briefly the field equations for mechanically and electrically anisotropic composites subject to the mechanical and electromagnetic loads. Some of the details of the current discussion and derivations may be found in [1].

Equations of motion for conductive solids in the presence of an electromagnetic field have the form

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} + \rho (F_i + F_i^L) = \rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} \quad (1)$$

Here σ_{ij} are the stress tensor components, u_i are the displacement components, ρ is the density of solid body, F_i are the body force components, F_i^L are the components of the Lorentz ponderomotive force. In the case of an electrically anisotropic but magnetically isotropic solid body the Lorentz force takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}^L = & \rho_e \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \times \mathbf{B} \right) + \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \times \mathbf{B} \right) \right) \times \mathbf{B} \\ & + \left(\left((\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon_0 \cdot \mathbf{1}) \cdot \mathbf{E} \right) \times \mathbf{B} \right)_\alpha \nabla \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \right)_\alpha + (\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the unit tensor of the second order, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the electrical permittivity tensor, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the electrical conductivity tensor, ε_0 is the permittivity in the vacuum, \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector, \mathbf{D} is the electric displacement vector, \mathbf{B} is the magnetic induction vector, \mathbf{E} is the electric field vector, ρ_e is the charge density, \mathbf{J} is the density of the applied electric current, ∇ is the gradient operator, and Einstein's summation convention is adopted with respect to the index α . The third nonlinear term in (2) is due to anisotropy in electrical properties (it vanishes when the electric field is isotropic),

and the last term attributes to the electric current that the solid body carries. As one can see, the Lorentz force in composites depends on the external electric and magnetic fields, magnitude and orientation of the electric current with respect to the magnetic field, and velocity and the rate of deformation of the solid. Maxwell's equations read as

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{div} \mathbf{D} &= \rho_e, \\
\operatorname{curl} \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \\
\operatorname{div} \mathbf{B} &= 0, \\
\operatorname{curl} \mathbf{H} &= \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and constitutive relations in electrically anisotropic but magnetically isotropic solids have the form

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{D} &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \mathbf{E} + \mu (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon_0 \cdot \mathbf{1}) \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \times \mathbf{H} \right), \\
\mathbf{B} &= \mu \mathbf{H} - \mu \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \times \left((\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon_0 \cdot \mathbf{1}) \cdot \mathbf{E} \right), \\
\mathbf{j} &= \boldsymbol{\sigma} \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \times \mathbf{B} \right) + \rho_e \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t},
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where μ is the magnetic permeability, \mathbf{j} is the current density vector and \mathbf{H} is the magnetic field vector. Furthermore, in conducting materials, the electric energy produced by the electrical current is converted to Joule heat. Thus the system of equations (1) and (3) has to be complemented by the heat transfer equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k} \nabla T) = -Q + c \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}. \tag{5}$$

Here T denotes the temperature, \mathbf{k} is the thermal conductivity tensor, c is the specific heat, ρ is the density, and Q is the Joule heat rate per unit volume, expressed in terms of the electromagnetic field components as

$$Q = \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E}. \tag{6}$$

The system of governing equations (1), (3), and (5) is essentially nonlinear and coupled in the dynamic problems. But even in a static setting, when equations of equilibrium (1) and Maxwell's equations (3) are uncoupled, the Lorentz force (2) may still be present in (1) due to, for example, an externally applied DC current (the last term in (2)). Then, Joule heat density Q due to the applied DC current takes the form

$$Q^{DC} = \frac{J_i^2}{\sigma_i} = \frac{I_i^2}{A^2 \sigma_i}, \tag{7}$$

where J_i is the density of the electric current, σ_i is electrical conductivity, I_i is the current, A is the cross-sectional area through which the current is passing, and subscript i indicates the current's direction.

Joule heating may play an important role in the mechanical response of electrified carbon fiber polymer matrix composites, since they possess relatively low (in comparison to metals) electrical and thermal conductivities. For instance, the electrical conductivity of the AS4 carbon fibers is $\sigma_x^{(f)} = \frac{1}{1.53} \times 10^5 \text{ 1/Om m}$. At the same time,

the electrical conductivity of copper is $\frac{1}{1.72} \times 10^8 \text{ 1/Om m}$, and, according to (7), the

Joule heat density produced in a carbon fiber by a DC electric current is three orders of magnitude larger than that produced in copper by the same current.

Lastly, we note that an impact of the electric heating on the composites will depend not only on the electrical and thermal properties of the composites and the density of the current applied, but also on the electrical contact resistance between the composite and electrodes.

BRIEF SUMMARY OF THE EXPERIMENTS

Experimental studies in [2-4] were directed towards experimental confirmation of the possibility to induce considerable changes in the mechanical response of composites by applying an electromagnetic field. Experimental studies included a series of low velocity impact tests on electrified unidirectional and cross-ply AS4/3501-6 carbon fiber polymer matrix composite plates. The tests have been carried out under 0A, 25A, and 50A DC electric current applied to the composites in the fiber direction. The results of measurements show considerable dependence of the impact-induced damage on the intensity of the electric field applied to the composite. In particular, when an electric current of 25 A and 50 A was applied to a unidirectional composite plate, the maximum load sustained by the plate has increased by as much as 24.7% and 43.6%, respectively.

Moreover, application of an electric current to cross-ply composite plates has reduced significantly the amount of the impact damage and increased the amount of the absorbed energy. For example, none of the tested cross-ply plates carrying a 50 A DC electric current were perforated in the impact tests conducted at the velocity (a velocity at which 50% of tested specimens are perforated and 50% are not), which was determined in tests with no current applied to the plates. Remarkably, the observed effect is amenable to active control, as higher magnitudes of the applied electric current lead to better impact resistance, and is reversible.

The results discussed above have been observed at short-term current applications, when the electric current was applied to composite plates immediately before impact. The outcomes of the impact tests on carbon fiber polymer matrix composites that we conducted under prolonged electric current application [3,4] were different: in contrast to a short-term current application that improves the impact response of the tested composite plates, a prolonged application of an electric current appeared to have a detrimental effect on the composites. In the tests an electric current was applied prior to

impact for a period of time necessary for achieving a steady-state temperature in the composite plate. A steady state temperature in the unidirectional plate subjected to a 25 A DC current was achieved after 24 min, with the temperature in the center of the plate surface reaching 35.94 °C and the ambient temperature staying at 23 °C. After that, an impact test was conducted with the current still passing through the plate. The impact velocity was the same as in the tests with short-term current applications. Although a prolonged application of the current increased the maximum load sustained by the plate, the subsequent failure induced a drop in the amount of the impact energy absorbed by the plate.

In the case of short-time current application, impact tests were conducted on the current-carrying composites immediately after the current was applied, so there were no temperature changes observed in the composites and, therefore, we can argue that an increase in the damage resistance occurred due to electromagnetic effects. In contrast, application of the electric current for an extended period of time led to significant heating, which eliminated the positive effect of the short-term current application. Preliminarily, it has been conjectured that the electromagnetic field effects play a dominant role when the current is applied for a short period of time, whereas the thermal effects suppress the electromagnetic effects during prolonged current applications.

DEFORMATION OF ELECTRIFIED COMPOSITE PLATE

We analyze deformation of a thin unidirectional composite (transversely isotropic) plate ($y - z$ is the plane of isotropy) of the thickness h due to Joule heating produced by a DC electric current carried by the plate in the fiber direction x . The density of the electric current applied is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}^* &= (J_x^*, 0, 0), \\ J_x^* &= J_0 = \text{const}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

We assume that the intensity of the current is such that a non-negligible temperature field is generated in the plate over some period of time. Moreover, we assume that strains are small and the thermal problem is uncoupled from the mechanical and electromagnetic problems: first, the heat transfer problem is solved and the temperature field due to applied current is found, which is subsequently substituted into the equations of motion or equilibrium. In addition to the temperature field, a DC current produces the magnetic field with induction

$$\mathbf{B}^* = (0, B_y^*, B_z^*), \tag{9}$$

which can be considered static. For a static problem the plate equations of equilibrium are

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial(N_{xx} + N_{xx}^T)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(N_{xy} + N_{xy}^T)}{\partial y} + \rho \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_x^L dz &= 0, & \frac{\partial(N_{yy} + N_{yy}^T)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(N_{xy} + N_{xy}^T)}{\partial x} + \rho \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_y^L dz &= 0, \\
\frac{\partial(N_{xz} + N_{xz}^T)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(N_{yz} + N_{yz}^T)}{\partial y} + \rho \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_z^L dz &= 0, \\
\frac{\partial(M_{xx} + M_{xx}^T)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(M_{xy} + M_{xy}^T)}{\partial y} + \rho \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_x^L z dz &= N_{xz} + N_{xz}^T, \\
\frac{\partial(M_{yy} + M_{yy}^T)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(M_{xy} + M_{xy}^T)}{\partial x} + \rho \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_y^L z dz &= N_{yz} + N_{yz}^T,
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where

$$\rho F_x^L = 0, \quad \rho F_y^L = -J_x^* B_z^*, \quad \rho F_z^L = J_x^* B_y^* \tag{11}$$

are components of the Lorentz force. Equations (10) are expressed with respect to the internal stress (N_{ij}) and moment (M_{ij}) resultants and thermal stress (N_{ij}^T) and moment (M_{ij}^T) resultants:

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{xx} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{xx} dz = hB_{11} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + hB_{12} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - A_1 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{zz} dz, & N_{yy} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{yy} dz = hB_{22} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + hB_{12} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - A_2 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{zz} dz, \\
N_{xy} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{xy} dz = hB_{66} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right), & M_{xx} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{xx} z dz = -\frac{h^3}{12} B_{11} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - \frac{h^3}{12} B_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - A_1 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{zz} z dz, \\
M_{xy} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{xy} z dz = -\frac{h^3}{6} B_{66} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}, & M_{yy} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{yy} z dz = -\frac{h^3}{12} B_{22} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \frac{h^3}{12} B_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - A_2 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{zz} z dz, \\
N_{xz} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{xz} dz, & N_{yz} &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_{yz} dz,
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{xx}^T &= (B_{11}\alpha_1 + B_{12}\alpha_2) \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \Delta T(x, y, z) dz, & N_{yy}^T &= (B_{12}\alpha_1 + B_{22}\alpha_2) \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \Delta T(x, y, z) dz, \\
N_{xy}^T &= B_{66}\alpha_6 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \Delta T(x, y, z) dz, & N_{xz}^T &= B_{66}\alpha_6 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \Delta T(x, y, z) dz, \\
N_{yz}^T &= B_{44}\alpha_4 \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \Delta T(x, y, z) dz,
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where the coefficients B_{11} , B_{12} , B_{22} and B_{66} are determined from the generalized Hooke's law

$$\begin{aligned}
B_{11} &= \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, & B_{12} &= \frac{E_2\nu_{12}}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, \\
B_{22} &= \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, & B_{66} &= G_{12}, & B_{44} &= B_{22} + B_{33} = G_{23}, \\
A_1 &= -\frac{\nu_{12}(1 + \nu_{23})}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, & A_2 &= -\frac{\nu_{23} + \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Here E_2 is Young's modulus for the isotropy plane, E_1 is Young's modulus for the direction perpendicular to the direction of the isotropy plane, G_{12} is the shear modulus for the direction perpendicular to the plane of isotropy, G_{23} is the shear modulus in the plane of isotropy ($y-z$), ν_{23} is Poisson's ratio characterizing the contraction within the plane of isotropy for forces applied within the same plane, ν_{12} is Poisson's ratio characterizing contraction in the plane of isotropy due to forces in the direction perpendicular to it, ν_{21} is Poisson's ratio characterizing contraction in the direction perpendicular to the plane of isotropy due to forces within the plane of isotropy. Furthermore, $\Delta T(x, y, z, t) = T(x, y, z, t) - T^{ambient}$ is the temperature difference in the plate caused by the electromagnetic field induced thermal load and α_1 , α_2 , α_4 , α_6 are coefficients of thermal deformation in (13). Equations (10) were obtained accepting the hypothesis of nondeformable normals and in the case of a transversely isotropic plate with $y-z$ plane of isotropy.

Let us analyze some special cases. If the plate is infinite and a DC electric current (8) is applied in the x -direction, the magnetic field generated in the plate by this current is

$$\mathbf{H}^* = (0, -J_x^* z, 0). \tag{15}$$

or

$$\mathbf{B}^* = (0, -\mu J_x^* z, 0). \quad (16)$$

Substituting (16) in (10) leads to disappearance of Lorentz force terms in the equations of equilibrium (10). The problem becomes thermoelastic. For any finite size plate subjected to an electromagnetic load the equations of equilibrium (or motion) will contain terms attributed to the present electromagnetic field as well as the thermal field induced by this electromagnetic field.

Now let us assume that the thermal field in the electrified plate has no variations in the directions perpendicular to the direction of an electric current, $\Delta T(x, y, z) = \Delta T(x)$, which is exactly the case of the described above experiments (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Diagram of the clamped plate in the contact with copper bars.

The equations of equilibrium become

$$\begin{aligned} B_{11} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + B_{66} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + (B_{12} + B_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} - (B_{11} \alpha_1 + B_{12} \alpha_2) \frac{\partial(\Delta T)}{\partial x} &= 0, \\ B_{22} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + B_{66} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + h(B_{12} + B_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} - B_{66} \alpha_6 \frac{\partial(\Delta T)}{\partial x} - \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} J_x^* B_z^* dz &= 0, \\ -\frac{h^3}{12} B_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} - \frac{h^3}{12} B_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} - \frac{h^3}{6} (B_{12} + 2B_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} - \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} J_x^* B_y^* dz - \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (J_x^* B_z^*) z dz &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Here $u(x, y, t)$, $v(x, y, t)$ and $w(x, y, t)$ are the corresponding middle plane displacement components. For instance, in the case of a clamped plate the thermal field will alter only the in-plane stress and strain components, whereas the deflection and transverse shear stress components will not be influenced by the induced thermal field. As soon as the temperature field is found by solving the heat transfer equations and the displacements in (17) are found, the stresses in the plate are determined from the generalized Hooke's law.

The computational results are presented for the clamped carbon fiber polymer matrix composite plate subjected to DC electric currents discussed above. The mechanical properties of the plate were as follows: $E_1 = 102.97$ GPa, $E_2 = 7.55$ GPa, $G_{12} = 3.93$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = 0.3$, $\alpha_1 = -1.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{1}{^\circ\text{C}}$, $\alpha_2 = 27 \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{1}{^\circ\text{C}}$, $\alpha_6 = 0$. The plate was clamped. Furthermore, a magnetic field due to the applied current was small and was neglected in computations and the thermal field was taken as one-dimensional and determined analytically by solving a corresponding heat transfer equation. Hence, due to the DC current the plate experienced only in-plane deformation, which is described by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} B_{11} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + B_{66} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + (B_{12} + B_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} - (B_{11} \alpha_1 + B_{12} \alpha_2) \frac{\partial(\Delta T)}{\partial x} &= 0, \\ B_{22} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + B_{66} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + h(B_{12} + B_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Figure 2 shows distributions of normal thermal stresses across the electrified unidirectional composite plate in the direction of the applied electric current (x -direction) for 25 A DC currents. Middle plane stresses are shown.

Fig. 2. Thermal stresses in the electrified unidirectional plate carrying 25A DC currents.

As one can see, application of an electric current results in a significant gradient in the σ_{yy} stress distribution, while stresses in the current direction (σ_{xx}) are of an order of magnitude lower. Moreover, stresses are quadratic functions of the applied electric current. It is also worth mentioning that the glass transition temperature of the considered composite was around 190 °C. Hence, electric current intensities used in computations were limited to those producing temperatures in the plate below the glass transition temperature of the composite.

Figure 3 shows contour plots of stresses at the middle plane of the composite plate subjected to 25A DC electric current in the fiber direction.

Fig. 3. Contour plots of the thermal stress (a) σ_{xx} , (b) σ_{yy} .

Thus, application of the electric current in the unidirectional carbon fiber polymer matrix composite plates leads to 1D thermal field that is practically constant in the directions transverse to the fiber direction. The thermal field induces only in-plane deformation with significant compression in the direction perpendicular to the applied current.

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